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FROM STANDARDIZATION TO CUSTOMIZATION: CHALLENGES FOR MARKETING OF SPECIAL INTEREST TOURISM DESTINATIONS OF ODISHA.

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Abstract

Dissatisfaction with present lot ,escape from day to day life, desire to see what remains at the other side of the mountain and beyond the next dark corner have propelled man to travel from time immemorial, to get pleasure, leisure, spiritual wellbeing, etc. Wide range of historical monuments, ecosystems, sea-beaches, rich art and culture attracts tourists to Odisha from world-wide.

Gradually tourists are looking for more Customized leisure & recreation experiences driven by the Specific Interest instead of established commercial & standardized tourism products, services and experiences. Odisha is blessed with wide range of wild- life sanctuaries, national Park, Buddhist destinations, Jain monuments, lakes, rivers, sea-beaches. The art, crafts, festival & ritual of Odisha is unique one. The tribal culture of Odisha is the biggest attraction for eco -tourism lovers.

In spite of all these attractions Odisha receives less than 1% of tourists who visits our country. This paper attempts to find out different challenges for marketing of those SIT attractions & destinations.

Key word: - Destination, Leisure, Special Interest, Eco- System.

Introduction:

Dissatisfaction with present lot, escape from day to day life, desire to see what remains at the other side of the mountain or beyond the next dark corner have propelled man to travel from time immemorial. Pleasure, leisure, recreation, business, adventure, nature, health, sports, pilgrimage, spiritual, cultural, park, wild life, conference, convention, shopping etc. are different tourist motivators which have attracted people from worldwide to India.

As described by “Mark Twain”: “India the Country under the sun that is endowed with an imperishable interest for prince & peasant, for lettered and ignorant, wise and fool, rich and poor, bounded and free, the land that all men desire to have seen & having seen once by even a glimpse would not give that glimpse for the shows of all the globe combined”. Wide range of historical monuments, religious places, mountains, ecosystems, sea-beaches of India are the reasons of tourism growth and expected to be the largest export industry in

near future. India gets around 7 million tourists from different parts of the world, which brings about 250 crore rupees through tourist spending.

Gradually tourists are looking for Customized Leisure & recreation experiences driven by the Specific Interest instead of established commercial & Standardized tourism products, services & experiences. SIT is going fast and evolving into a prominent form of niche segment i.e. alternative tourism form. Tourists are gradually preferring beautiful natures, warm welcome, home like place instead of standardized, overcrowded places. Special Interest tourism involves people with particular interest such as painting, cooking, bird watching, cycling, yachting debaucheries, food fair, farmers market, cooking shows, spirituality, sports etc.

Odisha is located in the east coast of India with a vast coastal length of 482 km and rich flora and fauna. Besides famous Konark and Puri temples, Odisha presents wild life tourism, eco-tourism, tribal tourism, art & craft tourism, cultural tourism etc to tourists from worldwide. Odisha is blessed with Asia's largest brackish natural water lake Chilika which involves millions of birds from far distance. Besides the bird sanctuary Chilika is famous for its population of Irrawaddy Dolphin a unique type in India. Odisha offers wide range of special Interest Tourism.

Objective of the study:

The primary objectives of this study are:-

1. To study about the reasons for the growth of SIT in Odisha.
2. To study on different alternative SITs of Odisha.
3. To study on different challenges of SITs of Odisha and its solutions.

Methodology of study:

Data collection:

Both primary and secondary data were collected for the study. For Collections of primary data 100 tourist including 15 foreign tourists were interviewed with structured questionnaires. Secondary data were collected from books, websites, internet, and annual statistics bulletins published by Department of tourism, Government of Odisha.

SPECIAL INTREST TOURISM DESTINATION OF ODISHA:

Odisha Tourism offers a wide range of experiences to tourists. But most of the tourists visit only Golden triangle of Odisha i.e. Puri, Konark and Bhubaneswar. Besides famous Konark, Puri and Lingaraj temple, Odisha is blessed with grand monuments, memorizing beaches, wildlife sanctuaries, rich culture and heritage, creative art & craft villages, ayurvedic treatment, mind blowing natural panaroma of tribal villages, dance festivals, crocodile parks and bird sanctuaries. Some of these famous & interesting tourism destinations of Odisha are described below.

Bhitarkanika National Park:

It is one of the most impressive wildlife sanctuaries of Asia covering an area of 672sq.kms of mangrove forest and wet land, the host of 215 species of birds, giant salt water crocodiles and numerous varieties of other animal species. The park includes mangrove forests, creeks, estuaries, rivers, back water and mud flats which are very significant for the ecological biological and geographical background of Odisha. The park is located at Kendrapada district of Odisha.

Chandaka Elephant Reserve:

Chandaka elephant reserve is of 193sq.km forest area located on the outskirts of Bhubaneswar which supports varieties of wildlife. Chandaka reserve have 30 species of

mammals, 27 species of reptiles and 120 species of birds. It is a famous place for eco-tourists & nature researchers.

Simlipal National Park:

Simlipal National Park spread over a sprawling area of 2750 sq.km at an altitude of 559.31 meters in Mayurbhanj district of Odisha is home town to three of India's biggest animal species Tigers, Asian Elephant and Gaur. The National Park hosts tiger, Leopard, elephant, bison, sambar, porcupine, pangolin, flying squirrel, hill myna, python etc. along with more than 1000 species of flowering plants.

Ushakothi Wildlife Sanctuary:

It covers 130sq.kms and small sanctuary located on Sambalpur district of Odisha a host of tigers, leopards, panthers, sloth bears & elephant.

Buddist Monuments:

Odisha is rich for Buddhist monuments like Dhauli, Lalitgiri, Ratnagiri, Udaygiri, Langudi etc. Lalitgiri (Located in Cuttack district), Ratnagiri & Udaygiri (Located in Jajpur Districts of Odisha) is known as three nodes of Diamond Triangles of Odisha. The same place which had attracted scholars from fifty different countries in the past was famously known as "Puspagiri Vihar" have been excavated by archeologists recently. The place is well connected by road and the majestic ruins of the Chaitya hall, number of votive stupas, are the main sources of attraction of tourists & researchers.

Jain Monuments:

Multi-storied ancient apartment residence of Jain monks are situated just 7kms west of Bhubaneswar in twin hills of Khandagiri. There are about 33 caves in both the hills with carvings of popular legends, historical scenes, religious functions and dancers.

Pattachitra's of Raghurajpur:

Raghurajpur one of the most famous village in Odisha is located in Puri district. The village is adopted by UNESCO and is famous for Patta painting and palm leaf painting. It is also the famous place of Gotipua dance.

Bird Watching at Chilika:

Chilika is the largest brackish water lake in Asia covering an area over 1100sq.km is a great attractive for bird watching & boating. In between October to February millions of migratory birds arrive in Chilika from far distance places like Siberia, China, Mogollia. Places like Mangal Jodi, Nalban are famous for bird watching.

Handicrafts in Odisha:

There are fifty recognized handicrafts in Odisha. The stone carving, wood carving, sand Art, metal work, silver filigree etc. earn an immense popularity with the development of tourism.

Tribal Culture of Odisha:

Tribal societies of Odisha are distinguished from complex or advanced societies of India and have a distinct style of life which can be best understood in the paradigm of nature, men and the supernatural. The Kutia kandha tribe and "Bonda" tribe have attracted many tourists to witness the relationship of humankind with nature.

Dance Festival of Odisha:

With numerous religions, ancient temples, Local shrines, tribal and an array of sacred places Odisha observes uncountable number of festivals and fairs round the year. Major festival of Odisha is car-festival of Puri and Durga Puja. Every year about 10 lakhs people gather during car festival at Puri to see the famous Chariot festival and gets blessings of the almighty. Other famous festivals which as special attractions are Kalinga Mahostav, Ekamra Utsav, Puri beach festival, Bali Yatra fairs of Cuttack, Tribal fairs at Bhubaneswar, Folk dance festival at Sambalpur, Chhow festival of Baripada etc.

TOURIST VISITS IN ODISHA:

Table No.1

Year	Domestic	Foreign	Total
2003	37,01,250	25,020	37,26,270
2004	41,25,536	28,817	41,54,353
2005	46,32,976	33,310	46,66,286
2006	52,39,896	39,141	52,79,037
2007	59,44,890	41,880	59,86,770
2008	63,58,445	43,966	64,02,411
2009	68,91,510	45,684	69,37,194
2010	75,91,615	50,432	76,42,047
2011	82,71,257	60,722	83,31,979
2012	90,53,086	64,719	91,17,805

(Source; Statistical Bulletin 2012, Dept. of Tourism, Govt. of Odisha)

There is a constant growth of about 9.5% tourists every year which is a good sign of tourism growth in Odisha. In spite of all effort Odisha gets less than 1% tourists every year. Out of total tourists West Bengal, Andhra Pradesh, Jharkhand, M.P, Chhattisgarh, Maharashtra & U.P contributes 30%.

INFRASTRUCTURES OF ODISHA

HOTELS OF ODISHA

:

Table No.2

District	No. of Hotels	No. of Beds.
Angul	28	1,590
Balasore	61	2,090
Bargarh	19	665
Bhadrak	25	757
Balangir	34	1,181
Cuttack	80	3,459
Ganjam	83	3,318
Jajpur	30	1,020
Kendrapara	21	284
Keonjhar	54	1,684
Khurda	201	9,787
Puri	444	19,639
Sambalpur	37	1,671

(Source: Statistical Bulletin 2012, Dept. of Tourism Govt. of Odisha)

In grand total Odisha have 1,457 hotels which can accommodate 60,077 people, at affordable tariffs.

Tourist Centers of Odisha:

Every district of Odisha is having tourist centers to help tourists. In total 329 tourist centers available through-out Odisha. There are about 60 approved excursion agencies in Odisha which can provide all kinds of tourism services to tourists.

AIR/Railway/Road Connectivity:

Odisha is very well connected to all major metro cities by air, railway & road. Very soon Biju Pattnaik International air port will start its functions and will be connected to rest of the world.

Findings of the study:

- About 75% of the tourists find Odisha as an attractive destination.
- 52% of tourist complaints against accommodation facilities & quality of services.
- About 70% of tourists find local transport facilities in SITs are below average type.
- 62% of tourists did not find proper guide services in SIT destinations.
- More than 80% eco- tourists feel it is unsafe to make night halt at special interest tourism destinations.
- Most people feel food quality is good in Odisha.
- 77% tourists find local people are shy and not friendly with tourists.
- 70% people opined to keep SIT Destinations very neat & clean.
- Among the respondents about 70% are not aware about many special tourist attractions of Odisha.

Challenges ahead for SIT Marketing:

Through Odisha is blessed with wide range of tourist attractions, the following challenges needs to be addressed soon.

- 60% of the tourists come to Odisha in between October to March. Marketing strategies are to be made for constant tourist flow to Odisha by promoting special interest tourism destinations.
- Since the abduction of Italian tourists by Naxalites foreign tourists are not visiting tribal dominated districts. State Government and Central Government must solve the Naxal issues & win the confidence of tourists soon.
- Local people must be encouraged to participate in tourism. Cab drivers, auto drivers, unemployed youths of local area must be trained for their capacity building enhancement. Fishermen of Chilika must learn different water sports from people of Goa.
- Flora & Fauna must be presented & promoted world- wide in line with Gujarat, Kerala & Goa tourism.
- Local entrepreneurs should go on study visit to Goa, Kerala, Rajasthan & Himachal Pradesh to learn about their active participation in tourism.
- There must be high tolerance to foreign culture.
- Government must take care of roads, parking, shopping complex, affordable accommodation, health services, internet connections, lighting of destination & cleanliness of the destinations.
- There must be effort for exploring, involving & developing neglected destinations having special attractions.
- Government must encourage women SHGS, individual household to participate directly in tourism growth of the state.

Conclusion:

The state is endowed with many special interest tourism attractions. A proper marketing strategy for promotion and intervention by government may boost SIT, which will further lead towards the development and promotion of other forms of tourism in Odisha.

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